

Potential and limitations of an EU Buyers' Club for carbon farming

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1. Introduction

Current EU land use practices are a major contributor to the climate crisis. At the same time, agriculture and forestry, and the ecosystems they depend on are extremely vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. This is not a distant scenario, but already the reality with livelihoods coming under increasing pressure from extreme weather, land degradation, water availability, and biodiversity collapse.

EU agriculture emissions accounted for approximately 365 million tonnes (Mt) of CO₂e in 2022, or ≈11% of the region's total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.¹ Drained organic peatland soils

in the EU emit another 220 Mt of CO₂e each year, of which three quarters (166 Mt, or ≈5% of total EU GHG emissions) is emitted by peatlands drained for agricultural production.² EU agriculture emissions have barely declined over the past two decades, and are not expected to decrease significantly unless additional measures are taken.³

Besides the significant emissions from agricultural activities, there is also the ongoing degradation of our natural ecosystems, including agricultural soils (60-70% of EU agricultural soils are degraded)⁴, which on top of its implications for biodiversity,

overall ecosystem health, and productivity, leads to a loss of biogenic carbon stored in soils and biomass, exacerbating the climate crisis. The EU's land sinks are faltering, and analysis shows that its carbon sequestration goal for 2030 is out of reach with the current trends.⁵

To have a healthy and resilient land use sector in line with planetary boundaries, things need to change.

So far, both regulatory and market initiatives have proven insufficient at incentivising a transition to sustainable land use. It is in this context that the European Commission has developed the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming regulation (CRCF), which establishes a framework for the generation of “carbon farming units” by eligible actors who choose to participate. These certified units of carbon sequestration and emission reduction are created with the aim of mobilising additional private finance through the implementation of, initially, sustainable agricultural management practices, agroforestry, rewetting of peatlands, and afforestation.

The CRCF does not exist in a policy vacuum. There are policies in place that govern decisions, trends, and practices in EU land use, which all closely relate to the generation and supply of carbon farming units, as well as policies that govern the potential demand for these units.⁶ Much of the focus over the past years among the Commission and stakeholders following the development of carbon farming in the EU, including the CREDIBLE project^{6,7,8} has been on the design of the CRCF methodologies and certification steps to make the supply side of generated units

coherent and robust. All of this activity took place while the CRCF development remained agnostic about the “use case” for the certified units (which was criticised by experts across the board because requirements can be dependent on use case).^{9,10} This is now changing, and the Commission's first answer to “what will happen with these units?” seems to be: an EU Buyers' Club.¹¹ This policy brief discusses the potential and limitations of an EU Buyers' Club for CRCF carbon farming units in the current policy context.

2. The CRCF carbon farming Buyers' Club

The question of financing and demand for carbon farming units has taken a central role in the policy discussion around the enabling and scaling of carbon farming in Europe. The Commission published a discussion paper that evaluates the potential of several financing mechanisms.¹² It shows that different financial solutions, such as funds or concessional loans, exist that could partially address the many roadblocks relating to challenging timelines and uncertainties faced by investors. Also considerations on the role of blended finance (i.e., mixing public and private finance) and the requirements for its success are discussed.

The report authors conclude that of the models they assessed, a Buyers' Club for carbon farming units comes out on top in the evaluation. This solution would consist in aggregating forward demand from public and private buyers into a pool and stimulating action through pre-purchase

agreements. According to the authors, this structure would be the best starting point, mainly due to its potential positive impact on demand and its ability to scale, while maintaining relatively low administrative complexity and limiting the Commission's own financial exposure. The report states that the convening and market-shaping role of the Commission could be used to strengthen demand for high-quality carbon credits, ensure their alignment with EU climate and environmental values, reduce current Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM) fragmentation, and decrease reputational and pricing risks for early movers. A two-year pilot is proposed for the implementation of the Buyers' Club with KPIs such as a minimum of two companies that commit to pre-purchase agreements resulting in the pre-purchasing of a minimum of 30,000 tCO₂e.

The Commission's report mentions the potential motivations of different types of buyers, and different potential rewards for the investment. However, critical to the outcome of such an initiative, ensuring it can be (part of) a high-integrity, effective, and science-based climate policy instrument, and thus requiring careful consideration and normative guidelines, are the surrounding climate policy as well as the design features of the Buyers' Club itself, such as its composition.

2.1. Climate policy flaws

2.1.1. Climate targets

In the absence of dedicated regulatory targets for emission reductions (as is largely the case in the agri-food sector), private buyers retain broad

discretion over how to achieve a net emissions outcome, including through investments in external emission reductions, carbon sequestration, or permanent removals. This flexibility is problematic because it blurs the mitigation hierarchy: emission reductions within a company's own operations and value chains are the essential cornerstone of climate action and should take precedence over external action. Where companies are permitted to substitute internal decarbonisation with the purchase of external credits—whether reduction- or removal-based—there is a material risk that internal mitigation efforts are delayed or deprioritised. A recent study shows that, while establishing a causal link between voluntary credit purchases and internal emission reductions remains challenging, reliance on external credits can, in some cases, slow the pace of internal emission reductions.¹³ It is a fact that there will be residual emissions far into the future, but the design of a net zero scenario with net targets along the way risks enabling a compensation logic that ignores the negative impact of emissions on the environment even when there is a corresponding removal. That would leave us with residual emission levels that are too high and removals and sequestration that do not have the climate impact they could have at lower residual emission levels. This demands a socio-political discussion and agreement on what constitutes a residual emission for a sector like agriculture, where the extent of achievable emission reductions is as much a matter of societal choices as it is a technical one.¹⁴

2.1.2. Claims

The motivation for many interested buyers of carbon farming units will be to use these units in the context of their company's climate action. Different types of claims exist. Compensation claims allow a buyer to offset their own emissions with purchased credits, while contribution claims allow a buyer to indicate that they have supported climate action with a certain budget.

To maintain the integrity and effectiveness of the initiative, only claims that are robust and in line with climate science can be allowed.

When it comes to carbon farming sequestration units and the accumulation of soil carbon, there are at least two big hurdles from a climate policy perspective. First, while soil quantification methodologies and protocols are advanced and under continuous development, the degree of quantification uncertainty remains such that these actions are currently not suitable to be translated into certifiable interchangeable units of mitigation.¹⁵ Given the possibility of overcrediting and lack of quality assurance, using compensation claims would be misleading and could put climate action at risk.^{16,17} Second, the inherent high risk of impermanence of the carbon stored in biogenic pools makes these units of carbon non-equivalent with emissions since they do not affect the long-term temperature, while emissions have lasting effects.^{18,19} Some have suggested that a centralised entity such as a European Carbon Central Bank could overcome the permanence challenge through

proper governance that could ensure perpetual removal (an uninterrupted chain of temporary removals).¹⁹ However, the authors note that even with such entity in place, and assuming functioning public governance, important challenges would remain. For example, the large carbon debt that a temporary removal entails could represent a significant future cost, which is among other things influenced by the opportunity cost and price of land, and may lead to nature-based removals becoming prohibitively costly at current market rates as well as potential moral hazard situations among companies that receive payment for credits and avoid the liability by going bankrupt. At policy level, no concrete plans for the creation of a European Carbon Central Bank have been presented. While perfection should not be the enemy of progress, we should treat this topic with the integrity the climate crisis commands, rather than lay the foundation for the next disappointment or scandal in the making. The Green Claims Directive was expected to bring clarity on the question of which types of credit purchases would allow for the different types of claims, but the legislation was put on hold and is unlikely to be revived anytime soon. In its position on the proposed Directive, the EU parliament suggested that only permanent carbon removals would qualify to compensate for fossil emissions. Another regulation that could have played a role by setting clear and stringent rules on how companies would need to report on their use of removals, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive, saw its scope adjusted to apply to fewer companies.

With the absence of a legislative framework, and the uncertainty that it creates, it is likely that many companies, fearing greenwashing backlash or sunken costs, will not commit to purchasing units of which the legal use is still unclear.

2.1.3. Carbon conundrum

Net targets and the compensation logic they enable, make carbon the objective, and as a result a valued commodity (see Climate targets section). At the same time, scientific uncertainty on the quantification and action-specific attribution of biogenic carbon, in particular soil carbon, makes these units a poor fit for compensation claims (see Claims section). Imposing a carbon market logic in which companies fund what from their perspective is cost-efficient mitigation is unlikely to result in the land use transition that the EU desperately needs (see Quality of change section). Due to these tensions around the motivation, the metric, the asset, and the outcome, it seems that carbon, although a relevant and important element, risks being used in the wrong way and for the wrong reasons.

Rather than a carbon-centric vision, a broader, more comprehensive motivation is needed, which can only be the sustainability and health of the systems on which activities rely.

The development of nature and biodiversity credits reflects the European Commission's attempt to move beyond carbon-centric metrics and to capture a wider set of ecological values, including

biodiversity, ecosystem integrity, and resilience. While the expansion of monitoring, reporting, and verification for ecosystems is a necessary and welcome step, the emerging nature credits framework risks reproducing and potentially amplifying the core weaknesses already observed in carbon markets. Uncertainties around baselines, additionality, permanence, and ecological causality are inherently more complex for biodiversity than for carbon, making integrity risks more acute. At the same time, the framework remains heavily dependent on voluntary demand and discretionary finance, with no clear or stable source of long-term funding. Without binding demand, clear restrictions on claims, and strong safeguards against substitution for regulatory compliance or genuine harm avoidance, nature credits risk creating an appearance of action rather than delivering systemic change. In the absence of robust governance, they may monetise nature symbolically, while deferring the harder political task of embedding biodiversity protection directly into land-use regulation, public budgets, and economic decision-making. The development of an independent, voluntary crediting approach for nature risks excluding adequate consideration of nature impacts of carbon farming actions. Given the potential impact of carbon farming actions on nature outcomes, consideration of nature impacts (minimising risks, maximising potential benefits) should be a more fundamental requirement for carbon farming certification under the CRCF.

2.2. Buyers' Club limitations

2.2.1. Voluntary effort

A wide array of voluntary schemes and standards exist for the certification and reporting of sustainability initiatives, such as Science Based Targets initiative (SBTi) for the target setting, certification methodologies such as Verra and Gold Standard to, in principle, ensure quality, Voluntary Carbon Markets Initiative (VCMI) for the responsible use of credits, Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) for reporting, ESG ratings to translate efforts into shareholder value, and benchmarks to increase transparency. At the same time, a different model has been developing in the agricultural sector, under the concept of regenerative agriculture, with organisations such as the Sustainable Agriculture Initiative (SAI platform), the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, the One Planet Business for Biodiversity, and Verra providing frameworks with tools and metrics to make agriculture more sustainable, including by reducing emissions and increasing removals alongside many other objectives, in ways that do not entail the use of credits in an offsetting or compensation logic. Still, the state of our environment and the emission trajectory speak for themselves, voluntary initiatives have not been able to transform EU land use practices at scale. Any voluntary framework is exposed to the obvious risk of low participation. In the case of the CRCF, this is true for the supply of units by land managers, as well as the demand for the units by private sector companies. The latter may induce the former, but voluntary demand is not

a given. The Label Bas Carbone (LBC), a carbon farming credit scheme that was launched in France in 2018 has experienced the issue of insufficient voluntary demand for the generated units, especially for agricultural projects. A large part of the LBC unit sales are instead coming from the legal obligation for airlines to offset the emissions from domestic flights.^{20,21} In practice, this means that in absence of investment, not much will happen, and that even with available funding, land manager participation is not guaranteed, and neither are the outcomes for the climate and the environment. An initiative relying on voluntary corporate sustainability cannot be seen in isolation from the current political climate. With environment and climate having fallen down the priority ladder of many EU leaders, and industrial interests increasingly steering policymaking²², companies may be less inclined to proactively invest in and commit to climate action, with some already backing away from earlier commitments.²³

With the regulatory basis providing the drive towards a target with regulated claims in return missing, is it really likely that an EU quality stamp will be sufficient to make investments flow?

2.2.2. Composition

Currently no type of company is excluded from the discussion on a Buyers' Club for the purchase of carbon farming units, meaning that buyers could be actors within or outside of land use value chains. If the main goal is to attract investment, one can choose to be agnostic about the source of capital and sell assets to the highest bidder. Who ends

up buying carbon credits, however, does have implications for sectoral contributions to climate action. Emission reductions in the land use sector should be achieved by the companies active in this sector, as the emissions constitute their scope 1, 2, or 3 emissions. At the same time, companies outside these value chains should prioritise and invest in reducing their own scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions, and not just meet their objective by buying emission reductions from agriculture or forestry if they happen to be low hanging fruits at a lower price. Buying outside the supply chain because it is convenient and cheaper is exactly the logic that resulted in a 2040 climate target that allows the use of international credits.²⁴ Ironically, these international credits might displace demand for the credits generated in EU projects and hamper the investment which this Buyers' Club is seeking to encourage. Carbon farming sequestration units are unfit for compensation claims (see Claims section). Meaning that for any private actor, whether within ('insetting') or outside ('offsetting') of the value chain, these should be purchased to make contribution claims. Rather than unrelated actors such as airlines or tech companies, one could imagine that companies inside the value chain would be willing to invest in sustainable land use practices. After all, if their business depends on the long-term availability and health of the land and other natural resources, it would be in their interest to support the transition to more sustainable land use, and consumers would welcome these contributions when they are promoted by the companies. However, many of these companies already have their own corporate sustainability programs, so whether they would see any added

value in following the EU methodology of the CRCF remains to be seen.

2.2.3. Quality of change

A Buyers' Club, and other voluntary corporate financing models for that matter, will only spur action if buyers perceive the return is bigger than the investment. This can lead to a race to the bottom and the use of shortcuts to achieve objectives, leaving meaningful action unaddressed, and further entrenching harmful and outdated business models. Unless companies are truly committed to an agroecological EU, in some individual cases over private profit, voluntary investments will not effect a transition. This is why targets derived from a vision for the future of EU land use and agriculture that meets all societal objectives is a fundamental starting point. Without it, a Buyers' Club will buy the cheapest mitigation benefits which will be those that do not require any fundamental change to the business model. For example, a food company selling livestock products will use feed additives (under discussion for inclusion in the CRCF) to reduce its emissions. Such "cost-effective" emission reduction completely misses the opportunity for the transformation of the sector which could yield benefits far beyond climate (strategic autonomy, health, animal welfare, etc).

2.2.4. Blending finance and ownership

A potential issue is the linkage between company-level carbon claims and national greenhouse gas inventory reporting. The coexistence of a top-down

accounting framework based on IPCC Guidelines and national GHG inventories and a bottom-up project- and methodology-driven approach under the CRCF may lead to tensions around attribution, double counting, and consistency. The combination of public and private funding can be useful. For instance, public funding could support activity startup costs, while private funding could support operation costs. This could also be done in a combination of activity- and result-based projects, which could be suitable for the type of projects in land use management.^{6,25} Clear rules will be necessary, as the allocation of outcomes from actions co-funded with public and private budgets can lead to difficulties.¹⁷

2.3. Buyers' Club potential

2.3.1. Funding

The Buyers' Club may generate some momentum and confidence which renews private sector interest in funding sustainable land management practices. Private sector funding could help closing the funding gap where public budget falls short. This is especially the case for afforestation and peatland rewetting which receive limited public support.

2.3.2. Testing

The financial commitments generated by the Buyers' Club could provide the support for a soft launch for the CRCF methodologies and certification protocols which can be tested. This could be a pilot phase to see if project developers

and operators on the ground manage to implement the methodologies in a satisfactory way. The pilot would also allow to test the alignment between accounting methods for CRCF outcomes at company and national inventory level, exploring whether they can be tracked and transparently reported, and where the limits of such alignment lie.

2.3.3. Harmonisation

The Buyers' Club could gather players from the agri-food sector that would be interested in following harmonised EU methodologies to support the transition to agroecological land management and food and fibre production. This opportunity to work towards a more harmonised understanding of sustainability indicators could link to the ongoing work on the on-farm sustainability benchmarking, as well as the nature credits. There is clear scope for alignment and mutual reinforcing between these different initiatives.

3. Policy alternatives

Many of the limitations of a Buyers' Club are inherent to its voluntary and corporate action nature. In light of the necessity and urgency to bring about change, an approach with more guaranteed effectiveness would be warranted. It is not a lack of ideas and proven solutions, but a lack of political capital for action on climate and environment that currently blocks more ambitious measures. Tools and solutions such as emission pricing under an Emissions Trading System (ETS) for agriculture, mandatory climate targets, Common Agricultural Policy funding and other subsidies with stronger

conditionality to gear land management practices towards nature friendly management with or without the use of the CRCF, have all been on the table, some for years, with studies and reports discussing various options.^{17,26,27,28} These alternative policy options also require careful consideration in their design to avoid triggering negative impacts such as the further intensification of animal agriculture to reduce emission intensities, the increased use of synthetic inputs, or reducing accessibility to healthy food for low-income groups. Their main strength is that these are regulatory instruments that do not have to rely on the willingness of for-profit actors.

It is possible to imagine a legislative framework that implements and goes beyond the polluter pays principle, based on the premise that an activity can only take place if it does so sustainably. What is needed is not a single instrument, but an effective policy mix in which different tools play clearly defined roles. Mandatory measures—regulation, standards, and conditionality—must set the baseline level of ambition and delivery. Economic actors also need long-term visibility on public policies that affect their environmental commitments, enabling them to modify their economic models and make long-term investments in sustainable solutions. Within such a framework, voluntary action can play a role, but only a limited and complementary one, as it can at best marginally increase ambition or accelerate delivery beyond what is already required. Nevertheless, with the new political reality and industry pressure, a sense of defeatism and self-censorship seems to have grown among policy makers which put these policy options out of reach in the near term.²⁹

Strengthening the public provision of farm advisory services and supporting the implementation of proven methods are high-impact, high-integrity, no-regret measures. A carbon credit has no intrinsic value and has in the past not been a guarantee for positive change. Hence, the objective is not to create an enabling environment for CRCF credits per se, which in absence of the right framework would not yield significant results. What ultimately matters is the change on the ground which leads to improved environmental and climate conditions.

An indispensable piece of the transition puzzle, regardless of the policy or financial instrument, will be good training for land managers which is based on healthy and sustainable practices, rather than advisory services from companies that sell inputs, or the requests from off-takers to increase productivity at all cost. The shift from land managers to land stewards—entrusted with responsibilities that extend beyond commodity production—can only occur if policy frameworks and value chains address the underlying economic realities of farming. Enabling stewardship therefore requires policies and market structures that reward sustainable practices through predictable income streams, reduced risk, and long-term profitability.

4. Conclusion

There is no doubt that restoring and maintaining ecosystems is an urgent need that requires enabling policy and funding. Typically, the improvement of the land and biomass health will come with an increase in sequestered carbon, and this will have a climate change mitigation effect. As such, carbon farming has a potential, but it is limited and carbon is not the only important metric, while it is mainly what is being measured and rewarded. In doing so, it may risk entrenching certain systems rather than changing them.

The CRCF aims to bring in private sector financing in addition to the existing public funding, closing the finance gap, and supporting the transition in the sector. Unfortunately, what we have been seeing is the backtracking on climate and environmental regulation, and reduced earmarked funding for environmental objectives, which is creating an even bigger gap between where we are and where we need to go.

The combination of diminished public financing and connected demands on the one hand and a nascent voluntary scheme relying on private sector buy-in on the other hand is an irresponsible high-risk bet.

Policy is evolving in different directions. Some elements are evolving towards more measuring, monitoring, and focusing on results, while at the same time scale and depth of reporting obligations, the regulation of claims, and harmonised dedicated funding for environment and climate are being

reduced. It is clear that the overall result is not a coherent framework that enables the necessary level of climate action and transformation in the land sector.

Due to a number of reasons such as the lack of regulatory basis and its voluntary nature, a Buyers' Club for carbon farming units is unlikely to save the day. At least, it is a forum for discussion on sustainability among agri-food actors. At best, it provides the financial support for a soft launch for the CRCF methodologies and certification protocols. It is however unlikely to provide a realistic projection of and form the basis of sustained demand. Eventually, a voluntary system will inevitably fall short as it will never reach the needed scale, nor is it the right basis for necessary measures that may require going beyond short-term business interests. While it can be seen as a first step, it may turn out to be a dear distraction and delay the start of an unavoidable compliance system, be it market-based or regulatory. Positioning the Buyers' Club as a primary "solution" risks allowing it to become a substitute for real reform. It signals action, convening power, and innovation, while implicitly deferring the politically more difficult—but systemically necessary—measures, including binding land-use standards, CAP conditionality linked to measurable outcomes, mandatory Scope 3 emission reductions, and guaranteed public payment schemes for ecosystem services. Without engaging explicitly with these trade-offs, the conclusion risks overstating the transformative potential of the Buyers' Club and understating the scale of policy intervention required to deliver durable change in agriculture.

A responsible and credible approach is to remove the illusion of choice regarding the transformation of EU land-use practices. Instead, the EU should adopt binding, science-based targets for land use that are consistent with the Paris Agreement and with ecological thresholds, recognising that continued delay or partial action is incompatible with maintaining climate stability and the integrity of natural systems.

From overarching EU targets that are compliant with the Paris Agreement and planetary boundaries, national and sectoral targets can be derived, to which Member States and private sector actors need to be held accountable. A credible policy approach must combine rerouting public funding to support the transition and duly regulating harmful practices with incentive structures such as pricing, standards, liability, and disclosure that compel private actors to internalise environmental costs and redirect capital toward desired outcomes that are systematically aligned with climate and nature objectives.

5. Policy recommendations

- Set separate EU and national climate targets for emission reductions, permanent carbon removals, and temporary nature-based sequestration, to ensure climate integrity and avoid mitigation deterrence.
- To set those targets, define sectoral residual emissions, not based on technical solutions applied to a business-as-usual scenario, but on a transformation of the land sector that achieves wider societal objectives, enabled by changes in production and consumption.
- Adopt strong regulation that sets the floor of performance for climate action and environmental protection in all land use, the legal minimum should be sustainability, and the appropriate policy instruments should be in place to guarantee this. Legal requirements should not be weakened or displaced by voluntary market mechanisms, as this risks a race to the bottom in ambition and integrity.
- Make sustainable practices the *conditio sine qua non* of access to public finance such as the CAP and encourage sustainability criteria in private finance such as bank loans. This will reach nearly all land managers whereas relying on voluntary CRCF and credit schemes means that only certain land managers will get involved.
- If establishing a Buyers' Club, consider it an experimental step to pilot the CRCF certification system that must be swiftly followed by revisions of the certification methodologies and process in the case of quality issues, and the implementation of a compliance framework that will deliver on environmental and climate objectives.
- Clarify the benefits for companies by regulating the use of credit purchases for claims. Given the uncertainty and impermanence associated with carbon farming sequestration units, they are not suitable for compensation claims and should

be limited to contribution claims. Emission reduction units should be purchased by value chain actors for scope 3 emission reductions.

- Set clear rules for allocation of outcomes between public and private funders of an activity and ensure that public money invested indeed enables and leverages private funding.
- Focus on regulated value chain investment in the resilience and long-term viability of production: if you can profit from it, you should protect it. This makes most sense as those actors have the most at stake and should therefore be motivated to support the right type of action, provided that harmful practices are banned so they cannot be part of the business models.
- Safeguard environmental integrity principles against short-term private business interests even in times of pressure on dedicated public funding.

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